

Inclusive Education: Importance and spread in modern education

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Abstract: *In modern education system, Inclusive education is gaining more importance and attention. The aim is to admit the children with special needs with normal class and in this classroom disable children and nondisabled children can learn together. Today's present study deals with Inclusive Education and its importance and spread. It also discusses about the position of Inclusive education in modern education system. Inclusive education emphasizes the equal opportunities for all learners. It belief that every student has the right to quality education. By UNESCO, 1994, — "Inclusive education is a process of addressing and responding to the diverse, needs of all learners by increasing participation in learning and reducing exclusion within and from education."*

Keywords: *Inclusive, non-discrimination, impairment, children with special needs, disability, Integrated Education.*

Introduction

According to Loreman and Deppeler, "Inclusive education means full inclusion of children with diverse abilities in all respect of schooling that other children are able to access and enjoy."

A child must receive education in an environment that is the least restrictive and is most conducive to his/her needs.

Children studying inclusive school to develop their confidence and to participate in social action.

It is an approach to schooling in which students with many different kinds of disabilities and learning needs are educated in classes with non-disabled and typically developing students.

Inclusive education promotes teaching strategies, curricula and school environment that accommodate diverse learning needs. It also emphasizes removing barriers to learning by providing support services, trained teachers and infrastructure.

The Salamanca statement and Framework for Action (1994) strongly promote "Inclusive Education" or "schools for All."

The present study deals with Inclusive education and its importance and spread.

Concept of inclusion:

'Inclusion is basic human rights.'

Inclusion means all children are welcome with their differences and all their disabilities. In this system, the emphasis on adapting the environment to accommodate.

Inclusive Education:

Inclusive education means, when a normal child and a child with special needs are in a same classroom and valuing them as a peer. All children do anything, only they need support and they also learn to the mainstream with those, who are not disable. We should belief that all children can learn at common school with their peers. Now Government of India works on them and has taken so many steps for them.

IEDC was set up 1974, to provide education for children with physical and mild mental disabilities within regular school, later updated 1992.

NPE 1986 commended inclusive education as a “goal to integrate the handicapped with the general community at all levels as equal partners to prepare them for normal growth and to enable them to face life with courage and confidence.”

“Person with disability Act” was set up 1995. This Act focused on mainly full participation. Equal opportunities, non- discrimination etc. After that in 2016, RPWD (Right to person with disabilities) replaced the existing PWD Act, 1995.

“PWD” (1995) focused on seven categories of disability. But In ‘RPWD’ (2016) disabilities increased twenty one.

Inclusive education means celebrating diversity.

Some Features of Inclusive Education:

- ◆ A philosophy of student, family and educator collaboration.
- ◆ Celebrating diversity and value all learners.
- ◆ Valuing educating learners in mainstream classrooms.
- ◆ Not forcing to collect marks in exam, but value their emotions.
- ◆ Equity is most important thing in inclusive Education.
- ◆ Inclusive education focus on equal opportunity for all learners
- ◆ It also focus on that disable and non-disable students learn together.

Important pillars of Inclusive education:

- ◇ Equity
- ◇ Diversity
- ◇ Belongingness
- ◇ Equal opportunity
- ◇ Non-discrimination

Concept of Impairment, disability and handicap:

The ‘World Health organization’ (WHO) in 1976 has made differences between the definition of Impairment, Disability and handicap.

Impairment:

Impairment is loss of organs or tissue.

Disability:

Disability means lack of ability, because of disability individual can’t do any activity like normal human being.

Handicap:

Handicap refers to disadvantages experiment by the individual, as a result of Impairment and disability. For that, individual can’t interact other people to the surroundings.

So, we can say that Impairment, disability and Handicap are not same thing.

Types of Disability:

The persons with Disabilities (PWD) 1995 have given seven types of disability.

1. Blindness
2. Low vision
3. Leprosy- cured
4. Hearing impairment
5. Loco motor disabilities
6. Mental retardation, and
7. Mental illness.

The Rights of persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016 expanding the recognized disabilities from 7 to 21. These are following

8. Dwarfism
9. Autism Spectrum Disorder
10. Cerebral Palsy
11. Muscular Dystrophy
12. Chronic Neurological Conditions.
13. Multiple Sclerosis
14. Speech and language Disability
15. Thalassemia
16. Hemophilia
17. Multiple Disabilities (including deaf Blindness).
18. Parkinson's Disease
19. Acid Attract victims
20. Intellectual Disability
21. Sickle cell Disease

What is Integrated education:

Integrate education means, disable persons are placed in regular classroom with some resources but they must fill pre- existing structure and environment which already exists in school. Its main limitation is that the school will not make any change; the school environment will remain the same that means child to adapt the school.

Differences between Integrate education and inclusive education:

- ◆ In Integrate education child adjust to the school, but in inclusive education school adjusts to the child.
- ◆ Integrate education has mostly same curriculum for all students but in Inclusive education there are flexible curriculum.
- ◆ Integrate education think that, disability is a child's problem but inclusive education think that disability as a social responsibility.
- ◆ Integrate education don't focus on child's need but inclusive education child centric with their unique needs.
- ◆ Integrate education can't improve child's confidence but inclusive education can do that.

Teaching Models of Inclusive Education:

Full inclusive model:

All students like disable or non- disable place in general education classes for the whole school day. General teacher and special education teacher teach them together, where special education teacher's role as a supporter or instructor. This model aims to serve all learners within same environment.

Particle inclusive model:

In this model, students spend maximum time in general classes but if they need only special services, then are pulled for specialized services.

Wang's Adaptive Learning Environment Model:

This model focuses on students learning or academic skills. It also helps to improve student's confidence in their ability and help them to interact social environment of school.

Team Teaching or co-Teaching:

In this model a general education teacher and a special education teacher join and work together as a partner and teach all students in same class. Here both

teachers are equally respected and trust each other.

The Strategic Intervention Model (SIM):

It focuses about the curriculum and the teaching method. It also focus how a student to do work together in a team. After check pre-knowledge of students then lesson plan is prepared.

Importance of Inclusive Education:

- It Beliefs all children can learn together both those disable and non-disable children.
- It reduces discrimination about sex, race, social and financial background etc.
- It strengthens social interaction with others.
- It strongly says that, children with disabilities can do any work and contribute economically to their communities.
- It includes all the children in normal classroom and main stream.
- It helps teachers to understand their student's strength and weakness. Because of that they can ready their learning strategy.
- Inclusive education can built nation.
- It improves self-confidence, for those children can think critically, make their own decision and solve problem.
- Students get opportunity to prove their abilities.
- Its aim to build democracy for all the children.
- It strengthens to education for all.
- It improves new methods, techniques, strategies and parameters in modern education.

Principles of Inclusiveness in schools by NCF 2005:

NCF published 1975, 1988, 2000 and 2005 by NCERT.

- Children do not fail; they only indicate failure of the school.
- Disability is a social responsibility accepts it.
- Learning together is beneficial for every child.
- Accept difference- celebrate diversity.
- All good practices of teaching are practices of Inclusion.
- Equal curriculum for all learners.
- Respects all children's unique needs and abilities.
- Focused on child centric education
- Emphasis on holistic development.
- Remember that, no student excluded from any ground like- race, sex, poverty family background etc.

Role of UNICEF to promote inclusive Education:

- To narrow the education gap for disable children.
- UNICEF promotes to influencing policy and school environment.
- UNICEF focuses on training teachers, students need and diversity.
- It is devolving the tools of data collection and the method of teaching.
- UNICEF focuses the plan to end discrimination in education system.
- Another role of UNICEF is to protect children's rights and their future.
- UNICEF works on early children equality, non- discrimination etc.
- UNICEF also focus on quality education they belief every child is unique and have their unique needs.

So, according to UNICEF, all children must get opportunities to improve their own ability.

Spread of Inclusive Education:

Presently Inclusive Education in India has improve itself through policies and programs, like IEDC (1974), SSA (2001), RPWD Act (2016), NPD (2006), RCI (1992), The National Trust Act (1999), UNCRPWD (2008) etc.

Through these policies, its aim is to involve children with special needs (CWSN) into mainstream programmed.

IEDC/Integrated Education for disable children (1974):

Integrated Education for disable children or IEDC was begin in 1974 through Govt. of India, initiated by ministry of social welfare. Its aim to integrate the students into regular class who have mild and moderate disabilities.

It was to promote holding the students with disability into the regular class, for this reason it provided with financial support for books, uniform and aids.

State Govt. provided little financial help to implement the program in schools.

Rehabilitation Council of India or RCI (1992):

RCI was the only statutory body for disable people. It had the responsibility of maintaining everything for PWD students.

RCI set up as a registered society in 1986 and it was become a statutory body on June 22, 1993 and after that it was further amended in 2000.

RCI (1992) Act, functions to regulate and monitor to disable persons for any service like standardize the syllabi. It working on special education and its research also.

The National Trust Act (1999):

National Trust Act was set up in 1999 for the person with Autism, cerebral palsy, mental Retardation and Multiple Disabilities.

This act to equip the person with disability to live independently to the community and improve their confidence and also interact with social people. This act focuses on the equal opportunity of those, who have any type of disability.

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan or SSA (2001):

- Focus on universalize elementary education.
- Introduce ‘Zero- rejection policy.’
- It focus on quality-based education
- Introduce ‘Multi- option Model’ for educating to the children with special needs.
- SSA developing Individualized Education plans for learning with parents and experts.
- SSA’s main aim to make ‘Education for All.’

National policy of Disability or NPD (2006):

NPD mainly deals with 3 area of disability– physical, Educational and Economical. It also focus on woman and children, social security, research, sports, regular information on disable person, non-government organization, issues disability certificate etc.

This policy believes that disable person is the valuable human resource for the developed country and provides them equal opportunity, full social participation.

United Nations Convention on the Rights of person with Disability or UNCRPWD (2008):

The United Nations Head quarter in New York. It was adopted on 2006 and force on 2008.

It makes a change on the attitudes to persons with disabilities. It says that, disabled people have to take their decision for their lives. It focuses on non-discrimination, respect etc.

This convention works on a wide range of areas like Health, Justice, and Education Employment etc.

RTE Act (2009):

This Act says that, free and compulsory education is a fundamental right for all children, between the age of 6-14 years. It focuses on holistic development, which means a student's all-round development. This act does not support discrimination based on caste, sex or religion. This act provides a better environment for diverse learners. It also focuses on equity means need-based education. It improves the confidence of each student to develop social integration

RTE or Right to Education Act emphasizes on continuous and comprehensive Evaluation (CCE). CCE means all-round development like physical, social, moral, emotional etc. The child builds self-image, self-concept.

NEP 2020:

It mainly focuses on socially and economically disadvantaged groups. It emphasizes inclusive education by equal opportunity, support for children with special needs, provide assistive technologies and many more. It also focuses on digital learning like ICT, AI to provide individualized learning for diverse learners based on their needs. It promotes child-centric education and learns them on their competency. Every child is unique, so they have their unique needs.

NEP 2020 emphasizes equity, diversity, all-round development etc. NEP 2020 plays an important role to promote inclusive education through flexible curriculum, unique teaching method and holistic development. Its aim is training for teachers to techno learning and encourage diverse learner needs.

Roles of school to promote Inclusive Education:

Schools play an important role in every student's life. The first responsibility they have to provide a warm classroom and safe environment to their students.

Classroom should be a place where the student feels that they are all here to learn, to think etc.

Inclusive school must modify their overall structure. But school faces so many challenges to promote inclusive education. These are following:

Infrastructure is a big problem for inclusive education.

Most of the teachers use specific teaching methods for diverse learners so this is another challenge.

Negative Attitude is a barrier, for that student can't improve their confidence.

Limitations of Inclusive Education:

In any education system teacher plays an important role, so its main limitation is lack of quality teachers.

Size of classes is another important part of inclusive education, because there are disabled and non-disabled students learn together. If a physically handicapped student wants to learn there who need wheel chair, of course the class should be big in size, so this is the biggest challenge.

Negative attitude is a common problem in present day, for that they can't improve their confidence about their ability.

Most of the time teachers use only some specific teaching methods, so all students can't adapt the same technique.

Limited Funding is another challenge for inclusive education.

Environment plays an important role in education system and it is a big problem in our country.

Conclusion:

This study helps to understand the importance of Inclusive Education. The main aim of Inclusive Education is to improve the social, Emotional and academic skill to all learners and promoting critical thinking. It focuses on justice, non-discrimination, equity. We believe that Inclusive Education is “Education for all.”

Inclusive education emphasis on every student uniqueness. It also a process where every student learn together. In Inclusive Education disabled children feel comfortable in the company of non-disabled children.

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